

Building a standardisation
culture in European Higher
Education: EDU4Standards
Highlights

- 15:00 | **Welcome & housekeeping**, Maria Giuffrida Trust-IT
- 15:05 | **Two years of EDU4Standards: an overview** Knut Blind, Fraunhofer
- 15:15 | **Knowledge Base (The ITCoS Concept):** Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS) foundations, Vladislav Fomin, Vilnius University
- 15:25 | **Toolkit: Teacher Support Tool:** Hub for teaching materials, best practices, and knowledge areas, Ivana Mijatovic, University of Belgrade
- 15:35 | **Courses: Completed Pilot Showcase** - Insights from delivered University and In-Company pilots:
 - Introduction: Pilot Design, Hugo Alexer Parada Gelvez, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)
 - Technology Battles, Geerten van de Kaa, Delft University of Technology;
 - Standardisation (Standardizacija), Ivana Mijatovic, University of Belgrade;
 - standardisation and Sustainability, Sokol Tominaj, TU Berlin;
 - Passion in Action, Nizar Abdelkafi, Politecnico di Milano;
 - Summer School, Elisabeth Staudegger, University of Graz;
 - Standardisation in High-Tech for Practitioners, Rudi Bekkers, Eindhoven University of Technology;
 - EARTO, Knut Blind, Technische Universität Berlin & Fraunhofer ISI;
 - Frederic Dufour, Small Business Standards
- 16:05 | **Quality Package: The EDU4Standards CWA**, Rudi Bekkers, Eindhoven University of Technology
- 16:10 | **Community: Platforms & Channels - EU Student Standardisation Association and Academic Standards Days**, Kirsten Glennung, CEN
- 16:25 | Q&A and Conclusions

Questions will be mostly addressed in the final part of the event
BUT...

Please ask your questions in the chat or Q&A box as soon as you have them

This will help us moderate efficiently

The recordings and slides will be available at edu4standards.eu

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Two years of EDU4Standards: an overview

Webinar
January 26, 2026

Fraunhofer

Knut Blind, EDU4Standards.eu Coordinator

- 🌐 Why can EDU4Standards make a difference also in the long run!
- 🌐 Education about standardisation is high on the agenda:
 - 🌐 EU Standardisation Strategy - > HLF
 - 🌐 EU Code of Practice on standardisation, European Standardisation Panel Survey
 - 🌐 US Standardisation Strategy incl. ANSI strategy, but also the plans and activities of the new administration
 - 🌐 National activities, e.g. in Germany, and international activities, e.g. ISO IWA 30, etc.
 - 🌐 High pressure due to demographic change & many new topics, AI, quantum, & challenges, i.e. climate change
- 🌐 Three prime keywords that will support us in creating impact, IMHO:
 - 🌐 **Branding:** People know us and our reputation;
 - 🌐 **Inclusivity:** Our network speaks for itself and we want to make sure all other education efforts related to standardisation in the EU (projects & partners can be integrated into EDU4Standards or at least be supported);
 - 🌐 **Sustainability:** We are dedicated to the topic since long time including EURAS as a hub, which should allow us to establish a sustainable initiative!

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Short name	Type	Country
1 (Coordinator)	Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research	FhG	RTO	DE
2	VILNIAUS UNIVERSITETAS	VU	UNI	LT
3	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	TUD	UNI	NL
4	TRUST-IT SRL	TRUST	SME	IT
5	COMMpla SRL (Affiliate of TRUST-IT)	COMM	SME	IT
6	UNIVERZITET U BEOGRADU - FAKULTET ORGANIZACIONIHR	UB	UNI	SRB
7	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	UNI	ES
8	Politecnico di Milano	POLIMI	UNI	IT
9	UNIVERSITAET GRAZ	UGZ	UNI	AT
10	Dublin City University	DCU	UNI	IE
11	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT BERLIN	TUB	UNI	DE
12	HOGSKOLAN I SKOVDE	SKO	UNI	SE
13	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT EINDHOVEN	TU/e	UNI	NL
14	TILBURG UNIVERSITY- UNIVERSITEIT VAN TILBURG	TiU	UNI	NL
15	COMITE EUROPEEN DE NORMALISATION	CEN	NPO	BE
16	Small Business Standards	SBS	NPO	BE
17	freesia innovation e.U.	FRE	SME	AT
18	House of Knowledge	HoK	SME	NO

WP / month, project month	Year																																													
	2024												2025												2026																					
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36										
WP 1 Project Management																																														
T 1.1 Technical and administrative coordination																																														
T 1.2 External Advisory Group (EAG) management			M1																																											
T 1.3 Ethics, data management, risk management, and compliance																																														
WP 2 Design teaching concepts in standardisation																																														
T 2.1 Define the intended learning outcomes (ILOs)																																														
T 2.2 Identify & categorise relevant existing content and methods																																														
T 2.3 Produce the innovative teaching concept											M2																																			
WP 3 Implementation																																														
T 3.1 Pilot design																M3																														
T 3.2 Pilot at university B.Sc level																																														
T 3.3 Pilot at university M.Sc level																																														
T 3.4 Extra-curricular pilots (including Seasonal School at unis.)																																														
T 3.5 Pilot of in-company training																																														
T 3.6 Pan-European EARTO pilot																																														
T 3.7 Evaluation of pilots																																													M5	
WP 4 Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability																																														
T 4.1 Communication, Engagement & Dissemination																																														
T 4.2 Development of a European Workshop Agreement																																														M6
T 4.3 Student Standard. Association & Academic Standards Days																		M4																											M7	
T 4.4 Exploitation plan and sustainability strategy for Edu4Standards																																														
T 4.5 Policy recommend. & Europ. standard. education roadmap																																														M8

Milestones

- M1** EAG established
- M2** Teaching concept completed
- M3** Pilot design completed
- M4** 1st series of St.Days + 1st draft of Tool Kit completed
- M5** Pilots evaluated, recomm. f. further impl. formulated
- M6** CWA completed
- M7** St.Days completed, Student St. Association established
- M8** Policy recommendations completed

The screenshot shows the homepage of Edu4Standards.eu. At the top right, there is a "Log in" link. The main header features the logo and tagline "Empowering Standardisation through Education". Below this is a navigation menu with the following items: Home, About (with a dropdown arrow), Teaching (with a dropdown arrow), Pilots, Academic Standards Days, Publications, and News & Events (with a dropdown arrow). The main content area has a large heading: "Empowering Standardisation through Education in Europe". Below the heading is the subtext: "Innovating how standardisation is taught in European Higher Education". To the right of the text is a photograph of a person presenting to a group of people in a lecture hall, with a red and green graphic overlay.

Log in

EDU4Standards.eu
Empowering Standardisation through Education

Home About ▾ Teaching ▾ Pilots Academic Standards Days Publications News & Events ▾

Empowering Standardisation through Education in Europe

Innovating how standardisation is taught in European Higher Education

KER#	Name	Exploitation lead
KER1	Standardisation knowledge base for the research & innovation community	FRE
KER2	Toolkit for Teachers and Curriculum developers	UB
KER3	Standardisation courses for teachers, students and professionals	TUD
KER4	Quality package for Standardisation Education for certification authorities, teachers, curriculum managers	TU/e
KER5	Policy package for Standardisation Education for policy makers	FhG
KER6	Support services for Standardisation Education	TRUST

EDU4
Standards.eu

Webinar presentation
January 26, 2026

Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS)

Prof. Vladislav V. Fomin
Vilnius University

Funded by
the European Union

 The **overall objective**: boost education about standardisation within European Higher Education Institutes

 5 key strategic objectives:

01 Develop and pilot an innovative teaching concept for standardisation (ITCoS)

02 Raise awareness through events (ex. Academic Standardisations Days)

03 Expand higher education courses on standardisation

04 Build a community of standardisation educators and learners

05 Establish an EU Student Standardisation Association

WP2: Design teaching concepts in standardisation

This means:

- 1. Translating the universal values and principles** as promoted by the EU into **specific contexts of standardisation.**
- 2. Help** existing **lecturers** of standards/standardisation **overcome topical gaps** in education about standardisation
- 3. Make it easy** for new lecturers **to start teaching** on the topic.

- Human-centred approach
- European values and interests
- Green & Digital skills & Gender equality

Expand the existing body of knowledge with **values-based** intended learning outcomes (ILOs)

What
is it?

- **Set of concepts, frameworks, and models** to stimulate supply and demand side of education about standardisation
- **Guide/compendium** for teaching EU core values, digital, green and gender skills in standardisation
- **Complementary material** to already existing (or new) teaching resources on standardisation

Who is
it
intend
ed for?

- **Experienced lecturers on standardisation** : to overcome topical and methodological gaps in education about standardisation
- **New lecturers on standardisation** : to overcome disciplinary and gender gaps in education about standardisation

We do we need a systemic approach?

- education about standardisation is **very fragmented**, it is not conceived nor practices as a stand-alone discipline;
- there are **no “best practices” or “standards” with regard to materials and methods** for education about standardisation;
- in delivering education about standardisation, a great variety of teaching methods and materials is used:
 - among the many topics and delivery methods, **no core method or topic** can be singled out.
 - more advanced levels of education about standardisation are delivered mostly by using **scientific publications as the main source of teaching materials – this implies students’ individual work and strong disciplinary bounding**
 - **the choice of methods and content for delivering education about standardisation highly depends on the lecturer – no education impact assessment efforts/results were identified.**

Distribution of tertiary education students by broad field and sex, EU, 2021 (%)

Make education about standardisation relevant and useful for different domains, levels of education, and genders

Number of tertiary education graduates in each detailed field of education, EU, 2021

Note: ranked on the total (male and female) share of students in each broad field
 Source: Eurostat (online data code: educ_uoe_enrt03)

How to educate on a) standard development, b) market competition, c) implementation of standards, d) promotion of awareness about standards, e) education about standards?

Most popular according to Eurostat* (the number of graduates each year, thousands)	Educational perspective on standardisation	Subject to great gender imbalance
Management & administration (200 BSc, 140 MSc), Business & administration (55 MSc)	Standards market competition; Selection of standards in new product development; Public procurement	
Nursing & midwifery (100 BSc), Medicine (110 MSc)	Uses of standards-based technologies and services	2,5x more female (Health and welfare)
Language acquisition (60 BSc)	???	2x more female (Arts and humanities)
Psychology (55 BSc, 35 MSc)	???	
Education science (55 BSc, 50 MSc), Training for pre-school teachers (55 BSc), Teacher training (55 MSc)	Safeguarding EU values and interests; Promoting awareness about the importance of standards	4x more female (Education)
Electronics and automation (55 BSc)	Development of standards; Selection of standards in new product development	3x more male (Engineering, manufacturing and construction)
Social sciences, journalism and information (the 5 th largest field by the percentage of students, BSc and MSc combined)	Promoting awareness about the importance of standards	2x more female

5 key strategic objectives of EDU4Standards.eu:

01 Develop and pilot an innovative teaching concept for standardisation (ITCoS)

- 02 Raise awareness through events (ex. Academic Standardisations Days)
- 03 Expand higher education courses on standardisation
- 04 Build a community of standardisation educators and learners
- 05 Establish an EU Student Standardisation Association

- The educational system –be it in Europe or globally – as comprised of educational technologies, administration and teaching practices, and the available learning resources, is best described as “**silo[ed]** with rigid, often impenetrable walls” (Bush & Mott, 2009, p. 12) .
- “Teachers and students are not free to choose the right / best / preferred tool for each teaching or learning activity they undertake, thus creating a **technology paradigm that artificially limits possibilities** and forecloses optimal teaching and learning choice” (Bush & Mott, 2009, p. 12).
- For the educational system, to trigger positive network externalities would require “**openness** combined with the principles of **modularity** and **interoperability** to facilitate the development of **new tools and methodologies** for **reusing, remixing, and mashing-up content** to achieve learning goals in ways never thought possible” (Bush & Mott, 2009, p. 5).

Bush, M. D., & Mott, J. D. (2009). The Transformation of Learning with Technology: Learner-Centricity, Content and Tool Malleability, and Network Effects. *Educational Technology*, 49(2), 3–20.

We propose the Framework Model of Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (FM ITCoS) to actively promote openness, modularity, and interoperability of educational and administrative resources

D2.1: ILO Framework – the hierarchical framework of intended learning outcomes for standardisation in line with EU interests and values

The Framework Model of ITCoS establishes the framework for the advancement of education about standardisation in accordance with the established practices of the educational domain and in support of EDU4Standards.eu project goals.

The Stand-EUVI Framework developed under T2.1 establishes the top-level of the hierarchical model with ILOs developed to foster EU competitiveness through standardisation and standards in line with European values and interests

T2.2 provided a comprehensive review of educational practices, materials, methods, and the overall EU educational landscape, which helps the patrons of education about standardisation establish relevance and seek high impact of their educational initiatives within the diverse landscapes of EU HE and job market

The ITCoS conceptualisation and the associated comprehensive catalogue of teaching topics and materials developed under T2.3, serve as a practical example of a didactic guide for implementation of education about standardisation.

creating the network effects through exchange & complementarities

NB: Network effects drive the adoption of a product or service!

When network effects are present:

- The value of a product or service increases as the number of users grows (or the other way around)
- They're among the most important reasons to pick one product or service over another

- **Exchange** : Easy sharing / exchange of teaching / learning resources
- **Staying power** : The long-term viability of a product or service (E.g., ASD, certification,...)
- **Complementary benefits**: Products or services that add additional value to the network (E.g., templates for course development; LO-repositories)

Level 4: Support // Implementation guides and aids.

Level-specific aims of the Framework Model of ITCoS	Examples of tools and actions to support the level-specific aims of the Framework Model of ITCoS	
Didactic guidance for HEIs (topics, materials, methods)	Identification and cataloguing of suitable content	Addressing the core-periphery design questions
Administrative guidance (course description and program needs justification templates)	Standards- / standardisation-related job market demand statistics;	policy overview for standards- / standardisation-related EU strategies / needs
Technical recommendations for Learning Object (LO) development and sharing	<p>There is a need for meta-standard to enable searching for and sharing Learning Objects, and referencing the ILO Framework;</p> <p>There is a need for easy import-export to popular LMS (Moodle and Canvas)</p>	<p>Suggest ILO-specific XML vocabulary for LO description</p> <p>Suggest/develop tools for searching & exchanging LOs</p>

Open Educational Resources (OER) are teaching, learning, and research materials that are freely accessible and openly licensed, allowing users to retain, reuse, revise, remix, and redistribute them (the "5Rs").

OER include full courses, modules, textbooks, lecture notes, assignments, simulations, and interactive learning materials. The defining feature is the use of **open licenses** (most commonly Creative Commons), which explicitly grant legal permission for adaptation

Institutional Support and Policy Endorsement

- **UNESCO:** Adopted the *Recommendation on Open Educational Resources (2019)*, promoting open licensing and international cooperation.
- **European Commission:** Supports OER through the Digital Education Action Plan and the Joint Research Centre (JRC).
- **Sustainability:** OER are increasingly linked to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and digital competence frameworks like DigComp.

Platform	Volume	Resource Types	Language(s)
<i>OERSI</i>	>100,000	PPT, PDF, Video, Interactive	DE, EN
<i>OERhub.at</i>	~2,000	Case studies, Guides, Teaching materials	DE
<i>UNA Europa</i>	~200+	Teaching units, Toolkits	EN
<i>OER Commons</i>	50,000+	Courses, Lesson plans, PPTs	Mostly EN
<i>MERLOT</i>	30,000+	Simulations, Case studies	EN

NB: Competence frameworks are usually supported only *implicitly via keywords*, not via structured, machine-readable metadata fields.

Platform	DigComp	SDGs	Edu4Standards
<i>OERSI</i>	Partial	Partial	No
<i>OERhub.at</i>	Limited	Limited	No
<i>OER Commons</i>	Partial	Partial	No

- 🌐 CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) to establish conditions to trigger the required network effects
 - 🌐 CWA to establish a common reference (document) for Edu4Standards-developed competence framework for education about standardisation
 - 🌐 CWA to establish a common reference (document) for Learning Object Metadata (LOM) use to standardise the “interface” with national and international OER repositories
 - 🌐 CWA to establish the Edu4Standards-developed Framework Model of ITCoS (aka “Pyramid model”) as a hierarchical management model for curricula development for and education about standardisation
- 🌐 Else?

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- 🌐 **Coordination:** Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft
- 🌐 17 partners (universities, HEIs, standardisation bodies and associations, and SMEs) from 11 countries

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 twitter.com/edu4standards

 [youtube.com/@edu4standards](https://www.youtube.com/@edu4standards)

Discover more

<https://edu4standards.eu/>

Toolkit: EDU4Standards Teacher Support Tool

Webinar
January 26, 2026

Ivana Mijatovic, University of Belgrade

Figure 3. The Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation Education (ITCoS)

Figure 3. The Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation Education (ITCoS)

KAs in the ITCoS enable

- a way to **systematise knowledge** and skills related to standardisation
- topics, existing teaching material (recommended books and research papers, teaching case studies, serious games, video material) and teachers' experiences (good practice).

The ITCoS is based on four KAs:

- 🌐 KA1. Basic knowledge of standardisation needed to raise awareness
- 🌐 KA2. Standardisation interdependencies with other areas and roles in specific contexts
- 🌐 KA3. Strategic use of standards
- 🌐 KA4. Strategic participation in standards development

Knowledge Areas (KA)	Industry and Market Needs for Education on Standardisation (Company Perspective) (Blind & Drechsler, 2017)	Knowledge Areas Topics
<p style="text-align: center;">KA1. Basic knowledge of standardisation needed to raise awareness</p>	<p>To know the basic terms used in standards and standardisation</p> <p>To know the standardisation institutions.</p> <p>To be able to search for and select appropriate standardisation organizations.</p> <p>To be able to judge which form of standardisation (formal vs. consortia) is appropriate</p> <p>To know the standardisation institutions' processes.</p> <p>To know the history of standardisation.</p>	<p>1. Why standards and standardisation are important?</p> <p>1.1. Topic: The Strategic Importance of Standards and Standardisation</p> <p>1.2. Topic: Technical, economic, legal, and societal implications and impact of standards implementation and participation in standards development (the European point of view)</p> <p>1.3. Topic: History of Standardisation</p> <p>2. What are Standards and Standardisation?</p> <p>2.1. Topic: Concept of Standards and Standardisation</p> <p>2.2. Topic: General objectives of standardisation, roles and domains of standardisation</p> <p>2.3. Topic: Types of Standardisation and Classification of Standards</p> <p>3. Who uses standards?</p> <p>3.1. Topic: Users of standards</p> <p>4. Who develops standards?</p> <p>4.1. Topic: Who develops standards?</p> <p>4.2. Topic: Consortia-based Standardisation</p> <p>4.3. Topic: Company Standardisation</p> <p>5. How standards are developed (basics)?</p> <p>5.1. Topic: How standards are developed within SDOs in Europe?</p> <p>5.2. Topic: How standards are developed within SDOs internationally?</p>

Knowledge Areas (KA)	Industry and Market Needs for Education on Standardisation (Company Perspective) (Blind & Drechsler, 2017)	Knowledge Areas Topics
<p style="text-align: center;">KA2. Standardisation interdependencies and roles in specific contexts</p>	<p>To be able to understand the interactions between standards and the regulatory framework</p> <p>To be able to understand standardisation in the context of the national quality infrastructure and the macroeconomic environment</p> <p>Company standardisation</p>	<p>6. European System of Standardisation 6.1. Topic: European System of Standardisation</p> <p>7. Interdependencies between Standardisation and Research 7.1. Topic: Interdependencies between Standardisation and Research</p> <p>8. Interdependencies between Standardisation and Innovation 8.1. Topic: Interdependencies between Standardisation and Innovation</p> <p>9. Interdependencies between Standards and Markets 9.1. Topic: Interdependencies between Standards and Markets 9.2. Topic: Interdependencies between Standards and Trade 9.3. Topic: Interdependencies between Standards and Public Procurement 9.4. Topic: Interdependencies between Standards and Policy 9.5. Topic: Standards Battles</p> <p>10. Legal aspects of standardisation 10.1. Topic: Legal aspects of standardisation</p> <p>11. SMEs and Standardisation 11.1. Topic: SMEs and Standardisation</p> <p>12. Quality Infrastructure (QI) 12.1. Topic: Quality Infrastructure (QI) 12.2. Topic: The Role of Metrology in the Quality Infrastructure (QI) 12.3. Topic: The Role of Standardisation in the Quality Infrastructure (QI) 12.4. Topic: The Role of Accreditation in the Quality Infrastructure (QI) 12.5. Topic: The Role of Conformity Assessment in the Quality Infrastructure (QI) 12.6. Topic: The Role of Market Surveillance in the Quality Infrastructure (QI)</p> <p>13. European Values and Principles & Standardisation</p> <p>14. Roles of Standardisation in Digital and Green Transformation</p>

Knowledge Areas (KA)	Industry and Market Needs for Education on Standardisation (Company Perspective) (Blind & Drechsler, 2017)	Knowledge Areas Topics
<p>KA3. Strategic use of standards</p>	<p>To be able to understand the impact of implementing standards</p> <p>To be able to search for and select appropriate standards</p> <p>To be able to implement standards in product or process development</p>	<p>15. Motives for and barriers to applying standards 15.1. Topic: Motives for and barriers to applying standards</p> <p>16. How to find the right standard? 16.1. Topic: How to find the right standard?</p>
<p>KA4. Strategic participation in standards development</p>	<p>To be able to understand the impact of standardisation processes</p> <p>To be able to identify the need for standards</p> <p>To be able to identify the need for getting involved in standardisation</p> <p>To be able to propose new work items in standardisation</p> <p>To be able to strategically influence the agenda in standardisation processes</p> <p>To be able to be passively involved in standardisation processes (observer)</p> <p>To be able to be actively involved in standardisation processes (participant)</p>	<p>17. Motives for and barriers to participating in standards development 17.1. Topic: Motives for and barriers to participating in standards development</p> <p>18. How to participate in Technical Committees (TCs) and Working Groups (WGs)? 18.1. Topic: How to participate in Technical Committees (TCs) and Working Groups (WGs)?</p> <p>19. How to identify the need for a new standard or improvement of an existing one? 19.1. Topic: How to identify the need for a new standard or improvement of an existing one?</p>

- The main intention of the EDU4standards.eu Teachers Support Tool, based on the ITCoS, is to become a focal point – the foundation for exchanging information, good practices and experiences, as well as teaching material .
- This guide provides key topics and concepts, recommendations for sources, support material, and good practice for tailoring part of the course or the whole course on standardisation.

Structure of the ITCoS guide (the EDU4standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool)	Explanation
1. Topic	Topics are chosen to represent a unit that educators can combine with other units of their choice. The topics are intertwined. It is recommended that all topics have SGD (social/green/digital) examples.
2. Short instruction	Short instructions elaborate on why understanding a specific topic is important or relevant
3. The ILOs examples	In this section is explained the connection with ILOs published in D2.1
4. Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious games/Other	The teaching case studies do not have to be written (although that would be good), but they can be described in a few sentences, and a list of sources can be given for a specific case (for example, HD vs Blue Ray). Sharing teaching case studies used in a classroom is a practice we must support.
5. Good practice	Good practice is a description of educators' experience in working with students/trainees. All partners and pilots should contribute to this part.
6. Recommended sources	It lists literature (books, papers) that is recommended to someone who wants to start teaching standardisation or to improve existing classes.

The screenshot shows the website header with the EDU4Standards.eu logo and tagline "Empowering Standardisation through Education". The navigation menu includes: Home, About, Teaching (selected), Pilots, Academic Standards Days, Publications, and News & Events. A dropdown menu for "Teaching" is open, listing: Teaching Concept, Teacher Support Tool, and Teaching repositories. The main content area features the text "EDU4S" and "Teacher Support Tool" in large font, with a red icon of two people sitting at a table below.

EDU4Standards Teacher Support Tool

Home

The EDU4standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool, based on the ITCoS, aims to serve as a focal point or central hub - a foundation for exchanging information, best practices, and experiences, as well as teaching materials related to standardization. Its purpose is to support educators in improving existing courses (or parts of them) on standardization or in integrating standardization topics into courses across various disciplines. This tool provides key concepts, recommended resources, support materials, and best practices for tailoring a course or course components on standardisation.

Explore the tool by clicking on the **four knowledge areas** below!

Basic knowledge for
raising awareness on
standardisation

Standardisation
interdependencies and
roles in contexts

Strategic use of
standards

Strategic participation
in standards
development

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Knowledge Area KA1: Basic Knowledge of Standardization for Raising Awareness

[Home](#) » [EDU4Standards Teacher Support Tool](#)

Knowledge Area KA1 focuses on systematizing knowledge, skills, topics, teaching materials, and existing best practices related to the fundamentals of standardization. If the learning objective is, for bachelor's or master's students, to understand the concept of standards and standardization, they must first be motivated to learn. This motivation is fostered by demonstrating the importance of standardization and its real-world applications.

For business students, motivation may stem from understanding the role of standardization in a business context, while for law or engineering students, the perspective might differ. Knowledge Area KA1 is essential for raising awareness and provides st

- WHY are standardization and standards important? (What is their strategic significance?)
- WHAT is standardization, and what are standards?
- WHO uses standards?
- WHO develops standards?
- HOW are standards developed?

1.1. The Strategic Importance of Standards and Standardisation

18 February 2025

1.2 Technical, economic, legal, and societal implications and impact of standards implementation and participation in standards development (the European point of view)

13 March 2025

1.3 History of Standardisation

13 March 2025

2.1. Concept of Standards and Standardisation

14 March 2025

3.1. Users of standards

Home » EDU4Standards Teacher Support Tool » Knowledge Area KA1: Basic Knowledge of Standardization for Raising Awareness

Generally, there are two types of standard users: direct and indirect. Direct users are those who implement the standards – or apply standards across a wide range of activities. Indirect users are those affected by the application of standards, such as consumers and services that comply with standards. Two aspects of standard users are their role in the development and the influence of indirect users on the evolution of standards. A standard is one that is widely accepted in the market. Most experts involve both direct and indirect users. However, the pool of direct users of standards (those who implement them) is much smaller than the pool of indirect users. Indirect users of standards could be pivotal in understanding the needs of a particular standard. Formal standardisation bodies do not collect data on who uses the standard.

Recommended teaching cases, serious games or other material

1. Case study

Case Study: Why do we use QWERTY? You're Doing it Wrong! Episode 5 | BBC Ideas:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AB9-qdPOTeg>

2. NSB material

Many NSBs provide free access to standards to educational institutions.

Please contact your NSB for more details, the complete list of the European NSBs can be found here: <https://sbs-sme.eu/standards-and-smes/standardisation-bodies/>

3. Good practice

To increase understanding of the role and power of users of standards the case on QWERTY keyboard can be used. The same case can be used for other topics too. The case QWERTY keyboard is good for explaining concepts installed base (in standardisation), dominant design, lock-in, and bandwagon effect.

Recommended sources

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/users-standards>

Other sources on the installed base:

- Farrell, J., & Saloner, G. (1986). Installed base and compatibility: Innovation, product preannouncements, and predation. *The American Economic Review*, 76(3), 893-906.

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8.1: Interdependencies between Standardisation and Innovation

Home » EDU4Standards Teacher Support Tool » Knowledge Area KA2: Standardization Interdependencies and Roles in Specific Contexts

Ideally, standards incorporate valuable and innovative ideas to represent the best technical solution to a problem. And the process of standardisation, in itself, can be a source of new innovative ideas as well. Hence, there are interesting interdependencies between standardisation and innovation. At the same time, some might have the feeling that standardisation and innovation are also opposites" (Perera, 2010), because the first appears to be about keeping things the same, whereas the second is about the development of new things. Firstly, there is the relationship between research and standardisation. While

research at universities creates knowledge at the frontiers of knowledge and has the potential to create standardisation (being a form of knowledge valorization), it is not easy to make this knowledge trans (2006) so stakeholders, such as the European Commission are investigating ways how the outcomes projects can be brought into standardisation (EC, 2023b). Economists are also conducting economic understand which scientific results are actually utilized in standards (Blind & Fenton, 2022). Secondly, trade, and standardisation. When standards perform roles, such as reducing variety, codifying knowledge they create economic effects, such as economies of scale, network effects, and reduction of transaction welfare (Swann, 2010a). Standards can remove trade barriers and promote open markets but can also. The development, use and national adoption of standards can create strategic advantages on the global

Recommended teaching cases, serious games or other material

1.Serious Game: The World of Standardisation (DIN)

Keywords: Standardisation & Innovations

About: The World of Standardisation (DIN) is interactive board game with objective to develop a strategic understanding about standardisation in innovation context. **Storyline:** Congrats, for you innovation you won the Innovation Trophy! It comes with some time and money. The game offers different choices: patent, standard national/ European/ international, specifications; and combinations are possible. Decisions to be made within the team. The game provides real-life-inspired standardisation situations, and it is designed to inspire questions.

Details:

- Time to play: according to decisions Ca. 30 min per round.
- Group size: played in teams of 2-5, max. 2 teams per board.
- Target group: students, founders
- Languages: English, German
- Contact: amelle.leipprand@din.de

Recommended sources

- Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice. ETSI (Vol. 2). (especially, Chapter 5 on standardisation and innovation, Section 5.3 on standardisation and research, and Chapter 7 on standardisation and IPR).
- Bekkers, R. (2017). Where patents and standards come together. In: R. Hawkins (ed.) Handbook of Standards and Innovation. Edward Elgar Publishing. DOI: 10.4337/9781783470082.
- Hawkins (ed.) Handbook of Standards and Innovation. Edward Elgar Publishing. DOI: 10.4337/9781783470082.

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- Baron, J., Spulber, D.F. (2018). Technology Standards and Standard Setting Organizations: Introduction to the Searle Center Database. *Journal of Economics and Management Strategy*, 27(3), pp. 462–503
- Bekkers, R., & Updegrave, A. (2013). A study of IPR policies and practices of a representative group of Standards Setting Organizations worldwide. Updated version. Washington, DC: National Academies of Science. Available at http://www.nap.edu/catalog.php?record_id=18510
- Bekkers, R., Blind, K., Coenen, H., Iverson, E. Jacobs, K., Hossain, K. (2006). Case studies on the interface between research and standardisation, and case studies on patent pools as a coordination mechanism. Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme, STREP, Priority 8, Contract 503 594.
- Bekkers, R., Duysters, G. & Verspagen, B. (2002). Intellectual property rights, strategic technology agreements and market structure: The case of GSM. In: *Research Policy* 31(7) 141-1161. DOI: 10.1016/S0048-7333(01)00189-5.
- Bekkers, R., Henkel, J., Tur, E.M., Vorst, T. v.d., Driesse, M., Kang, B., Martinelli, A., Maas, W., Nijhof, B., Raiteri, E., Teubner, L. (2020). Pilot study for essentiality assessment of Standard Essential Patents, Thumm, N. editor(s), EUR 30111 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, JRC119894, doi:10.2760/68906, ISBN 978-92-76-16666-5.
- Bekkers, R., Tur, Elena M., Henkel, Joachim, Vorst, Tommy van der, Driesse, Menno, Contreras, Jorge L. (2022). Overcoming inefficiencies in patent

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How to contribute to the EDU4standards.eu Teacher Support Tool

- 🌐 If you have already developed teaching materials...
- 🌐 If you know of any existing papers or publications on the topic...
- 🌐 If your project includes training materials on standardisation...
- 🌐 If you have an idea related to the topic but no time to develop it...
- 🌐 If you have experience training students in standardisation and would like to share...

LLC. <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9780792386384>.

- Gaillard, J. (1933). A study of the fundamentals of industrial standardisation and its repository.tudelft.nl/record/uuid:eb5dd4a5-6b5a-4af5-ae8a-197de0cfc78.
- Hesser, W., Feilzer, A., & de Vries, H. J. (2010). Standardisation in Companies and publication/337160610_Standardisation_in_Companies_and_Markets_3rd_Ed.
- Murphy, C., & Yates, J. (2013). The International Organization for Standardisation: and Non-State Actors: Whose Standards Whose Development, 81–94. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781482277388>.
- Spivak, S., & Brenner, C. (1993). Standardisation Essentials: Principles and Practice. doi.org/10.1201/9781482277388.
- Wiegmann, P. M., de Vries, H. J., & Blind, K. (2017). Multi-Mode Standardisation: A 1386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2017.06.002>.
- Wiegmann, P. M., Eggers, F., de Vries, H. J., & Blind, K. (2022). Competing Standards 51(2), 104427. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2021.104427>

Would you like to improve this content? Leave a comment!

How to contribute to the EDU4standards.eu Teacher Support Tool

- If you want to share experience in standardisation but you have no idea how to write **your** teaching case study ...
- If you want to participate in creating teaching materials ...
- If you want to review the new ...

Join our collaborative work group

EDU4
Standards.eu

*Thank You for Your
Attention!*

Let's shape the future of
standardisation education

[ivana.mijatovic@fon.bg.ac.rs]

Funded by
the European Union

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Courses: EDU4Standards.eu Pilot Showcase

Webinar
January 26, 2026

Hugo Alexer Parada Gelvez, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Main results

- Eight pilots covering ILOs levels 4–8, with 236 teaching hours dedicated to standardisation across diverse target audiences:
 - University bachelor's level (UB)C
 - Two university master's level pilots (TUB, TUD)
 - Two extracurricular pilots (POLIMI, UGZ)
 - Two in-company pilots: Lifelong Learning (TU/e, SBS)
 - One pan-European pilot (FHG)
- Key educational gaps addressed:
 - Teaching methods
 - Teaching content
 - Lack of certification
 - Gender perspective
 - Lack of reflection on values and European interests
- Best practices and lessons learned from pilot implementation
- Practical application of ITCos
- Open Call for pilots' initiative

- **Objectives** “Develop and pilot in-company course on standardisation for a demanding and rich environment”
 - Integrate European values & interests
 - Integrate company-specific views & policy
 - Develop re-usable materials
 - Obtain experience for future efforts inside and outside the project
 - 5 developers/trainers, serious game (HoK)
- **Target:** Professionals working in an -tech context (rich and demanding business environment)
- **Timeline:** 25H1: First two courses, 26H1: Third course
- **Location:** Eindhoven, The Netherlands

Main results

- Very positive evaluation, enthusiastic participants, interaction
- Significant efforts in organisation (program) and logistics (venue, catering, etc.) paid off
- Format with short (30 min.) sessions and many breaks works
- Good network building between participants
- Clear communication on expectation, setting, confidentiality, etc
- Created 11 sheet decks that can be re-used

Learning & reflection

- ILO's hard to map to this audience
- Takes lot of efforts to get participants
- Trade-off in-person or online
- Adapting to diverse audience in levels & expertise

- **Objectives:** "Develop the Stand-EUVI summer school for educators" (+ researchers, + TTOs)
 - Introduction of 26 participants from very different professional fields and backgrounds to the concept of standardisation in line with EU values and Interests ("Stand-EUVI")
 - Starting with values, 12 speakers from academia and standardisation bodies provided short input about standardisation, standards and practice, each ending with small assignments (questions on how the content could be integrated into their own field)
 - Based on a "peer-to-peer" approach, exchange of participants was encouraged
 - Emphasis on the European values and interests in standards and standardisation
- **Target:** Educators; during planning, it became apparent that academic educators are mostly also researchers who wanted to learn how to transfer research into standards; technology transfer officers (TTOs)
- **Timeline:** September 2025, 2 weeks online on Moodle (kick-off, material, getting to know each other); 3+2 days in person in Graz
- **Locations:** University of Graz, Faculty of Law

Main results

- Urgent need for training emphasized by educators, TTOs
- Researchers showed great interest in actively engaging
- Treat teachers/researchers/TTOs what they are: experts in their respective field
- Short inputs, immediately followed by small tasks for application in the respective work area, were a good idea; however, the participants opted for heated discussions.
- Alternate serious/difficult content with light-hearted (video “My Favourite Standard”, educational games; walk&talk, etc.); coffee and lunch breaks are valuable time for personal reflection.

Learning & reflection (personal thoughts)

- Trust in the power of the group – educators already know what they want to teach/train
- Three days of face-to-face teaching + online platform are a perfect fit; five days in a row is too long for professionals
- Online sessions are difficult; they could work (better) with active moderation (more like “interviews”)
- The intensive exchange on the topic of Stand-EUVI was great fun! =)

- Objectives: "Develop an extracurricular course on standardisation for engineers"
 - Introduce students to the concept of standardisation and its role in engineering, innovation, and industry
 - Familiarize participants with key standardisation organizations and processes (e.g., CEN, CENELEC, ETSI, ISO, IEEE)
 - Highlight the strategic importance of standards for technology development, interoperability, and market access
 - Emphasize the link between standards, standardisation and European values
- Target: MSc and BSc engineering students
- Timeline: November-December 25, 3 sessions, 12 hours
- Locations: One session hybrid, one session only in-presence (Serious game), and one session only online

Main results

- Very positive evaluation of the course
- High motivation for the topic
- Students understood very well the relevance of standardisation for engineering, innovation, and competitiveness
- Excellent exam results
- Students asked "what's next"

Learning & reflection

- Attracting students is the main challenge
- Teaching by question works extremely well
- Serious games are key success factor
- Hybrid delivery is essential
- Online delivery enables scalability

- **Objectives:** provide researchers with a concise yet in-depth understanding of standardisation as relevant from a Research and Technology (RTO) perspective, skills to operate in standards bodies, and enable senior researchers to exploit standardisation for their RTO's business models (e.g., IPRs, SEPs, Open Source).
- **Target:** Researchers affiliated to institutions organized within EARTO differentiated into beginners, intermediate and sophisticated experts
- **Timeline:** Pre-pilot addressing Fraunhofer researchers in May-June 2025; Pilot in November-December 2025
- **Location:** six online webinars
- **Main results:** Almost 2000 registrations, almost 900 participations by almost 400 participants

- **Main results, learnings and recommendations**
- effective in reaching a large number of researchers
- little interaction and feedback, but evaluation is still missing (base: around 50 answers)
- replication easily possible and expansion to further target groups, e.g. Marie Curie Alumnis

EDU4Standards.eu

Pilots

EDU4Standards is implementing a series of pilot programmes designed to help test and refine the learning of standards in school educational and professional settings across Europe. These pilots are central to our mission of enhancing standardisation education, addressing the critical need for skilled communication experts, and ensuring that the curriculum remains relevant and effective for each country's specific needs.

Each pilot is carefully designed to test the **Iterative Teaching Concept of Standards Education (ITCE)** across different educational environments, including:

- **University courses:** Tailored to fit into existing bachelor's and master's degree frameworks, focusing on embedding standardisation into a wide range of disciplines.
- **Skills-transfer activities:** Including research schools and workshops, these pilots aim to offer practical, hands-on experiences with standardisation.
- **Company Training:** Targeted at professionals, these pilots aim to enhance the standardisation skills of current and future members within various industries.
- **Post-European-Initiative:** Collaborating with research and technology organisations (RTOs) across Europe to broaden the reach and impact of standardisation education.

The following pilot initiatives have been successfully delivered by the EARTO towards completion partners, showcasing the project's ongoing commitment to developing standardisation skills across education and training.

Open call for pilots

EDU4Standards is implementing a series of pilot programmes designed to help test and refine the learning of standards in school educational and professional settings across Europe. These pilots are central to our mission of enhancing standardisation education, addressing the critical need for skilled communication experts, and ensuring that the curriculum remains relevant and effective for each country's specific needs.

The consortium of EUS 14 Standards.eu has developed an innovative learning network, master agreements and an implementation guide (ITCEG) for education and training of future European standardisation experts. This will be tested in the pilot phase.

To enhance the impact, the consortium seeks standardisation professionals interested in the new level of education in standardisation. Teachers, lecturers or any other professionals from the EU or associated countries, which want to set up a pilot based on the ITCEG in their own country and to submit proposals for the Open Call for Pilots on Education for standardisation Education in standardisation leading to not needed.

You are encouraged to explore your own learning activities. From our network you will get advice and support.

The first stage of the call was closed to June 2025 with a deadline on 30th December 2024 17:00 Brussels time.

Applications for phase 1 will be invited to provide counter submissions for phase 2.

Applications who have already passed phase 1 will be invited to proceed to phase 2 with a deadline on 31st December 2024 17:00 Brussels time.

Check for further details: [EDU4STANDARDS Open Call for Pilots](#)

[CALL DOCUMENT PHASE 1](#)

[SUBMIT TO PHASE 2 HERE](#)

EDU4Standards.eu

Funded by the European Union

Project number: 101019787 - Horizon Europe

Programme under Grant Agreement no. 101019787

Privacy policy

- **Objectives:** The main objective of the course is to provide students with fundamentals and more advanced knowledge of standardisation and to broaden and tie this knowledge to various fields such as sustainability, geopolitics, gender issues, artificial intelligence, blockchain, ethics etc.
- **Target:** Bachelor and Master students of all degrees
- **Timeline:** Winter semester (October 2025 – March 2026)
- **Location:** Technical University Berlin, Chair of Innovation Economics

Specific aspects:

- Large part of lectures is conducted by guest lecturers from associations, SDOs, industry, academia..

Main results, learnings and recommendations

- Number of enrolled students: ca. 30 students
- Students are highly motivated and enjoy guest lectures
- Students are very keen on “not being greenwashed”, i.e. they really want to learn about sustainability issues and not only hear buzzwords
- Guest Lectures were highly succesful

In times of AI and online entertainment, it is hard to make students come to the lectures.

Challenges:

- To keep students interested and coming to the lectures
- Active participation in class

- **Objectives:** The main objective of the course is to provide students with advanced academic knowledge in the field of standardisation, helping them understand its importance and impact of standardisation, and the application of standards, in various markets and modern business practices.
- **Target:** Bachelor students, Business studies (Second year - age of enrolled students 20 years)
- **Timeline:** Summer semester (May –July 2025 online; March – June 2026 onsite)
- **Location:** University of Belgrade, Faculty of Organisational Science

Specific aspects:

- Improvement of existing course, established 2011, 2015, 2019

Main results, learnings and recommendations

- Number of enrolled students: 439
- Students are highly motivated to solve industry problems (role of standardisation consultants).
- want to see the bigger picture (e.g., how one solution can change the world, and what happens if that solution becomes a standard).
- less motivated to analyse literature (e.g., standards).
- quite motivated to write scripts and use AI apps (50% of successful assignments)

Challenges:

- To provide good quality digital teaching material
- Informative websites of SDOs becoming important for teaching
- To show the real world of standardisation – now

Teaching small groups is completely different from teaching large groups.

Teaching younger students is very different from teaching older students.

Objective:

- Design and develop an educational serious game in standards competition

Target

- Master's students in innovation management, engineering, and policy

Timeline

- **Phase 1:** Conceptual design & model formulation (completed)
- **Phase 2:** Game mechanics, digital support, scenario development (ongoing)
- **Phase 3:** Classroom pilots, evaluation, and iterative refinement (May-June 2026)
- **Phase 4:** Finalization and dissemination within the EU network

Trial runs: EU partner institutions (June)

Preliminary results: A hybrid game based on a simplified dynamic model

- **Objectives** “Develop and pilot a course on standardisation for SMEs”
 - Integrate European values & interests
 - Reinforce the importance of standards for business strategy
 - Collect SME feedback on relevance and alignment with SMEs needs/reality
 - Develop re-usable materials
 - Obtain experience for future efforts inside and outside the project
 - 5 developers/trainers, serious game (HoK)
- **Target:** Professionals working in SME organisations/intermediaries and SMEs
- **Timeline:** 26H1: SBS members (English) and Sectoral Organisation (English/German)
- **Location:** Online and hybrid (Germany – TBC)

Quality Package: The CEN Workshop Agreement

Webinar
January 26, 2026

Rudi Bekkers, Eindhoven University of Technology

“A standard is a technical document designed to be used as a rule, guideline or definition. It is a consensus-built, repeatable way of doing something.”

Source: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/european-standardisation/european-standards/>

- We want standards education to be based on consensus, a repeatable way of doing something!
- So why not create a standard for it?
- Edu4standards took the initiative for this and we had a kick-off meeting in Dec 2025 with >35 participants from within and outside edu4standards
- Project Plan has now been formally adopted, officially launching the drafting phase of our CEN-CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA).

Formal scope:

“Provide guidelines for a competence framework, teaching and training methods and training content for education on standards and standardisation. The overarching goal is to strengthen the competencies of students, professionals and other learners, taking European values and interests into account.”

Is aimed to align well with HLF proposed “Pan-European Certificate of Knowledge in Standardisation” which is currently implemented by CEN/CENELEC/ETSI

Work on the CWA will continue throughout 2026.

Community: EU Student Standardisation Association and Academic Standards Days

Webinar
January 26, 2026

Kirsten Glennung, CEN

Edu4standards.eu will build the first ever European Standardisation Students' Association

WHAT

- A forum by students for students, supported by the standardisation community
- An alternative way to build skills and CV
- A privileged insight to an important backbone of the single market and the European Competitiveness

WHY

- Ageing standardisation experts
- Need to ripe the benefits of standardisation across industry and R&I
- Need for understanding of the societal value of standardisation and the role of Europe in international standardisation

1

Input from ASDs on best practices

2

NSBs organizing ASDs proposes activities for ESSA

3

Open call to students' interested to co-create ESSA

4

Focus group meeting with students

ESSA
Official Launch
Q2 2026

- 🌐 **Academic Standard Days** are stand-alone **interest creating** events at higher education institutes across Europe targeting students in the domains of engineering and business among others
- 🌐 The **aim** is to strengthen the link between **standardisation and R&I** as well as address the need to form the **next generation of standard drafters**
- 🌐 The events will also contribute to **increasing visibility** of standardisation at HEI with the possibility of **replication of the ASD concept** post project

*For the lessons
we learned
check the ASD
Handbook*

Stockholm

- One day event
- Hosted by NSB
- Focus: ICT & Cyber security
- Presentations, panels, case study, industry mingle

Madrid

- Two half-day events (one for students, one for teachers)
- Hosted by Uni
- Presentations, panels, game café, young professional testimonials

Milano

- One day event
- Hosted by Uni
- Focus: circular economy
- Presentations, panels, workshop, industry mingle

Berlin

- One day event
- Hosted by NSB
- Presentations, panels, serious games, industry networking, quiz, case studies, video making

Ljubljana

- 3 consecutive afternoons
- Hosted by University
- Presentations, case studies, hackathon and sparring with company representatives

Nicosia, 29 March

Iasi, 28 May

Graz, June

Belgrade

And more destinations to come

Helsinki, October

Dublin, October

Do you want to help us co-create a new European student network around standardisation, skills, and career opportunities?

We are looking for students who are curious, motivated to connect with peers across Europe, and interested in how standards support innovation, industry, and European competitiveness

The ESSA will be co-created by students, together with the Horizon Europe project Edu4Standards.eu and CEN and CENELEC

The ESSA is open to students matching the following criteria:

- Area of study: any discipline
- Level: Bachelor's, Master's, PhD (or equivalent)
- Where you study: any EU country
- Language: fluent English

Students will have opportunities to take on leading roles within the Association, including:

- organisation and governance
- debates and community discussions
- events and networking
- capacity building and learning activities
- career and employability initiatives

It will be possible to participate in focus group meetings on either 11 feb 12h30, 12 feb 8h30 or 17 feb 17h30

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